

Cyclic Voltammetric Studies on some Copper Dithiocarbamates

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Cyclic voltammetry at Pt-electrode in acetone/TBAP has been carried out on $\text{Cu}(\text{R},\text{dtc})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{R},\text{dtc})_2\text{ClO}_4$, and $\text{Cu}(\text{R},\text{dtc})_2\text{-py}$ ($\text{R} = -\text{C}_2\text{H}_5, -\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, and $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$) systems. Two redox couples $\text{Cu}(\text{R},\text{dtc})_2^+ + e^- = \text{Cu}(\text{R},\text{dtc})_2$, and $\text{Cu}(\text{R},\text{dtc})_2 + e^- = \text{Cu}(\text{R},\text{dtc})_2^-$ have been observed in each case.

Dithiocarbamates as ligands have unique characteristics of stabilising both low and high oxidation states of transition metal ions¹. This is specially true in case of copper, where alongwith the common oxidation state Cu^{II} in $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$, copper-dithiocarbamates are also known for both Cu^{I} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2]_2$ (Ref. 2) and for Cu^{III} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2]^+$ (Ref. 3, 4) and $\text{X}_2\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})$ (Ref. 5). It is interesting, therefore, to examine the redox behaviour of copper-dithiocarbamates.

Consistent and significant substituent effect for the one-electron oxidation and reduction for $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$ at the platinum electrode was recorded by Chant *et al.*⁶. Randle *et al.*⁷ studied the reduction of a series of $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$ complexes in propylene carbonate at the mercury electrode by a variety of electrochemical techniques and showed that the complexes undergo reduction in two successive one-electron diffusion-controlled steps with associated adsorption of the complexes and the reduction products. Most recently, Hendrickson *et al.*⁸ reported electrochemical oxidation and reduction of sixteen $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$ complexes using normal-, pulse-, AC-polarography and cyclic voltammetry at a platinum electrode to show that $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$ undergoes single one-electron oxidation and reduction steps yielding respectively $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2^-$. In the present work we have carried out cyclic voltammetric studies on the systems, $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2\text{-pyridine}$.

Results and Discussion

Cyclic voltammograms have been recorded at platinum electrode in acetone with tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte. Following systems have been studied: (a) $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]$, (b) $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$, (c) $[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2]$, (d) $[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$, (e) $[\text{Cu}(\text{n-pr}_2\text{dtc})_2]$ and (f) $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2 + \text{pyridine}]$. Representative cyclic voltammograms ($\nu = 200 \text{ mV/s}$) are shown in Fig. 1 (a-f), and the CV parameters are collected in Tables 1 (a-f).

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms ($\nu = 200 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$).

TABLE 1(a)—CV-PARAMETERS* FOR $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_3\text{dtc})_2$

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$							Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$						
	E_{pa}	E_{pc}	$E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pa}	i_{pc}	i_{pc}/i_{pa}	$-E_{pc}$	$-E_{pa}$	$-E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pc}	i_{pa}	i_{pa}/i_{pc}
25	0.575	0.510	0.54	60	5.00	4.750	0.95	0.56	0.49	0.52	70	5.25	5.00	0.95
50	0.585	0.512	0.54	70	6.75	6.250	0.92	0.56	0.48	0.52	80	7.00	7.25	1.00
100	0.590	0.520	0.55	70	9.87	10.000	1.01	0.56	0.48	0.52	80	9.75	8.75	0.89
150	0.585	0.515	0.54	70	12.25	12.250	1.00	0.56	0.48	0.52	80	11.75	11.00	0.93
200	0.580	0.510	0.54	70	13.75	14.125	1.02	0.56	0.48	0.52	80	13.75	12.75	0.92
250	0.585	0.510	0.54	70	16.00	16.00	1.00	0.56	0.48	0.52	80	15.50	14.50	0.93
300	0.580	0.510	0.55	70	17.00	17.50	1.02	0.56	0.48	0.52	80	17.00	15.50	0.91

*All currents in μA , all potentials in V vs SCE.

 TABLE 1(b)—CV-PARAMETERS* FOR $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_3\text{dtc})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$							Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$						
	E_{pc}	E_{pa}	$E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pc}	i_{pa}	i_{pa}/i_{pc}	$-E_{pc}$	$-E_{pa}$	$-E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pc}	i_{pa}	i_{pa}/i_{pc}
50	0.500	0.570	53.5	70	3.85	3.25	1.00	0.56	2.50	53.0	60	2.00	1.50	0.75
150	0.515	0.575	54.0	60	5.25	5.75	1.09	0.55	0.48	51.5	70	4.25	2.50	0.58
250	0.510	0.575	54.0	60	6.75	5.50	0.81	0.56	0.48	52.0	80	4.75	3.37	0.70
300	0.500	0.570	53.5	70	8.00	8.34	1.04	0.56	0.47	51.0	90	6.00	3.05	0.50

*All currents in μA , all potentials in V vs SCE.

 TABLE 1(c)—CV-PARAMETERS* FOR $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{chx}_3\text{dtc})_2$

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$							Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$						
	E_{pa}	E_{pc}	$E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pa}	i_{pc}	i_{pc}/i_{pa}	$-E_{pc}$	$-E_{pa}$	$-E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pc}	i_{pa}	i_{pa}/i_{pc}
50	0.440	0.385	0.410	60	3.50	3.750	1.07	0.71	0.61	0.660	180	3.25	2.50	0.76
100	0.440	0.380	0.410	60	5.00	5.375	1.06	0.71	0.61	0.660	100	4.50	3.50	0.77
150	0.450	0.390	0.420	60	6.25	7.000	1.12	0.70	0.60	0.650	100	5.25	3.00	0.57
200	0.445	0.390	0.420	55	7.25	8.250	1.10	0.71	0.60	0.655	110	6.25	4.75	0.76
250	0.440	0.380	0.410	60	8.00	8.850	1.09	0.72	0.59	0.655	130	7.25	5.75	0.79
300	0.450	0.380	0.415	60	8.50	9.250	1.08	0.71	0.58	0.645	130	7.50	6.25	0.83

*All currents in μA , all potentials in V vs SCE.

 TABLE 1(d)—CV-PARAMETERS* FOR $[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_3\text{dtc})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$							Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$						
	E_{pa}	E_{pc}	$E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pa}	i_{pc}	i_{pc}/i_{pa}	$-E_{pa}$	$-E_{pc}$	$-E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pa}	i_{pc}	i_{pc}/i_{pa}
50	0.62	0.38	0.500	240	8.75	5.50	0.62	No well defined peak observed.						
100	0.66	0.39	0.525	270	11.25	5.25	0.46							
150	0.67	0.32	0.520	300	13.25	8.50	0.64							
200	0.68	0.37	0.535	310	13.50	9.00	0.66							
250	0.70	0.37	0.535	330	14.75	9.25	0.62							
300	0.72	0.37	0.545	360	13.75	10.50	0.76							

*All currents in μA , all potentials in V vs SCE.

 TABLE 1(e)—CV-PARAMETERS* FOR $\text{Cu}(\text{npr}_3\text{dtc})_2$

Scan rate mV s^{-1}	Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$							Couple $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$						
	E_{pa}	E_{pc}	$E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pa}	i_{pc}	i_{pc}/i_{pa}	$-E_{pc}$	$-E_{pa}$	$-E^{0'}$	E_p mV	i_{pc}	i_{pa}	i_{pa}/i_{pc}
50	0.565	0.500	0.53	65	4.50	3.50	0.77	0.57	0.49	0.53	80	4.25	4.25	1.00
100	0.555	0.490	0.52	65	6.25	6.75	1.08	0.57	0.48	0.52	90	6.25	5.75	0.92
150	0.560	0.495	0.52	65	8.25	8.25	1.00	0.57	0.48	0.52	90	7.50	7.25	0.96
200	0.560	0.495	0.52	65	9.75	9.25	0.94	0.57	0.48	0.52	90	9.00	8.25	0.91
250	0.525	0.495	0.51	65	11.25	11.00	0.97	0.58	0.48	0.53	100	10.00	9.50	0.95
300	0.560	0.495	0.52	65	12.50	12.25	0.98	0.58	0.48	0.53	100	11.00	10.50	0.95

*All currents in μA , all potentials in V vs SCE.

TABLE 1(f)—CV-PARAMETERS* FOR Cu(et₂dtc)₂-PYRIDINE SYSTEM

Scan rate mV s ⁻¹	Couple Cu ^{II} /Cu ^{III}							Couple Cu ^{II} /Cu ^I						
	E _{pa}	E _{pc}	E ^{o'}	E _p mV	i _{pa}	i _{pc}	i _{pc} /i _{pa}	-E _{pc}	-E _{pa}	-E ^{o'}	E _p mV	i _{pc}	i _{pa}	i _{pa} /i _{pc}
25	0.54	0.50	0.52	40	1.00	1.00	1.000	0.55	0.50	0.540	50	1.75	1.50	0.85
50	0.53	0.50	0.51	30	1.75	1.25	1.710	0.55	0.50	0.550	50	2.25	2.00	0.88
100	0.53	0.49	0.51	40	2.05	2.00	0.730	0.56	0.50	0.530	60	3.25	3.25	1.00
200	0.54	0.49	0.51	50	4.25	3.25	0.765	0.56	0.50	0.530	60	4.75	4.50	0.94
300	0.55	0.49	0.52	60	5.50	4.25	0.773	0.57	0.49	0.530	80	5.75	5.75	1.00
400	0.54	0.48	0.51	60	6.25	4.00	0.640	0.56	0.48	0.525	70	6.50	6.25	0.96
500	0.54	0.48	0.51	60	7.25	6.00	0.830	0.56	0.49	0.525	70	7.50	7.25	0.96

*All currents in μA, all potentials in V vs SCE.

Bis(dithiocarbamato)copper(II): Among this class, we have studied only three compounds, viz. Cu(et₂dtc)₂, Cu(n-pr₂dtc)₂ and Cu(chx₂dtc)₂. Cyclic voltammetry of Cu(et₂dtc)₂ and Cu(chx₂dtc)₂ have earlier been reported by Hendrickson *et al.*⁸ with tetraethyl ammonium perchlorate as supporting electrolyte. Randle *et al.*⁷ also reported the CV behaviour of dialkyl dithiocarbamates at hanging mercury drop electrode. Our CV results on the three Cu(dtc)₂ complexes are similar to those obtained by Hendrickson *et al.*⁸. For each of the three complexes studied two one-electron redox couples have been observed. These redox couples apparently involve the following electrode reactions,

The parameters for the two couples for all the three complexes (scan rate=200 mV s⁻¹) are given in Table 2 for ready comparison. Cu^{II}/Cu^{III} couple for the three complexes show the anodic-to-cathodic peak separation (E_p) of 70, 65 and 55 mV respectively, as against the theoretical value of

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS FOR Cu^{II}/Cu^{III} AND Cu^{II}/Cu^I COUPLES

(a) Cu ^{II} /Cu ^{III} couple							
Complex	E _{pa} V	E _{pc} V	E _p mV	E ^{o'} V	i _{pa} μA	i _{pc} μA	i _{pc} /i _{pa}
Cu(et ₂ dtc) ₂	0.58	0.51	70	0.54	13.7	14.1	1.02
Cu(npr ₂ dtc) ₂	0.56	0.49	65	0.52	9.75	9.25	0.94
Cu(chx ₂ dtc) ₂	0.44	0.39	55	0.42	7.25	8.25	1.10
(b) Cu ^{II} /Cu ^I couple							
Complex	-E _{pc} V	-E _{pa} V	E _p mV	-E ^{o'} V	i _{pc} μA	i _{pa} μA	i _{pa} /i _{pc}
Cu(et ₂ dtc) ₂	0.56	0.48	80	0.52	13.75	12.75	0.9
Cu(npr ₂ dtc) ₂	0.57	0.48	90	0.52	9.00	8.25	0.9
Cu(chx ₂ dtc) ₂	0.71	0.60	110	0.65	6.25	4.75	0.8

59 mV for a reversible one-electron redox couple at 25°. The ratio of the cathodic and anodic peak currents i_{pc}/i_{pa} for all the complexes is 1.0±0.1. These characteristics speak of reversible nature of

the step-1 for all the three complexes. For Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple, the cathodic-to-anodic peak separation (E_p) is 80, 90 and 110 mV. These values are considerably higher than the theoretical value of 59 mV for one-electron reversible redox process, suggesting that the electrode processes are only quasi-reversible. The quasi-reversibility of Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple has earlier been attributed⁶ to the relaxation process involved in a stereochemical change from square-planar copper(II) to tetrahedral copper(I); the univalent copper (3d¹⁰) strongly prefers a tetrahedral structure⁹. The extent of irreversibility for Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple for the three complexes follows the order: Cu(et₂dtc)₂ < Cu(npr₂dtc)₂ < Cu(chx₂dtc)₂. The peak current ratio (i_{pa}/i_{pc}) is less than unity, indicating that the electrode process is not fully reversible.

Cu(et₂dtc)₂-py system: For Cu(et₂dtc)₂, we also carried out the CV studies in presence of pyridine, keeping Cu(et₂dtc)₂: py ratio as 1:100. The cyclic voltammograms are given in Fig. 1(f) and the CV parameters are presented in Table 1(f). For the purpose of comparison of the CV behaviour of Cu(et₂dtc)₂-py system with that of Cu(et₂dtc)₂, the parameters (scan rate 200 mV s⁻¹) are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3—PARAMETERS OF Cu^{II}/Cu^{III} AND Cu^{II}/Cu^I COUPLES

(a) Cu ^{II} /Cu ^{III} couple							
Complex	E _{pa}	E _{pc}	E _p mV	E ^{o'}	i _{pa}	i _{pc}	i _{pa} /i _{pc}
(et ₂ dtc) ₂ Cu-py	0.54	0.59	50	0.515	4.25	3.250	0.8
(et ₂ dtc) ₂ Cu	0.58	0.51	70	0.545	13.75	14.125	1.0
(b) Cu ^{II} /Cu ^I couple							
Complex	-E _{pc}	-E _{pa}	E _p	-E ^{o'}	i _{pc}	i _{pa}	i _{pa} /i _{pc}
(et ₂ dtc) ₂ Cu-py	0.56	0.50	80	0.53	5.75	5.75	1.0
(et ₂ dtc) ₂ Cu	0.56	0.48	80	0.52	13.75	12.75	0.9

It may be noted that the formal standard electrode potential (E^{o'}), i.e. (E_{pc}+E_{pa})/2 for the Cu^{II}/Cu^{III} couple shows a small decrease from 0.54 V vs SCE for (et₂dtc)₂Cu to 0.52 V for (et₂dtc)₂Cu-py and that for the Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple has shown a very small decrease from -0.52 V for (et₂dtc)₂Cu to -0.53 V for Cu(et₂dtc)₂-py. It may be inferred

that $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ -py system is slightly easier to oxidise and harder to reduce. In view of the fact that $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ forms adduct¹⁰ with pyridine (the base occupying the vacant axial coordination positions), the observed change in CV behaviour may be explained in terms of the change in the electronic

structure. A simple viewing at the structures of $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ (structure A) and $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ -py (structure B) suggests that the central atom in (B) will have higher electron density than in (A). Evidently, therefore, losing of electron (oxidation) will be easier for (B) than for (A), and similarly, gaining of electron (reduction) will be harder for (B) than for (A). These observations are in support of the suggestion⁷ that the electroactive centre in $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ complex is the central metal ion.

The other notable change in the CV behaviour of $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ -py system compared to $(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2\text{Cu}$, is considerable decrease in the current which have been reduced to less than one-third for $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ step and to less than half for $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ step. One of the reasons for this decrease may be the increase in the size of the complex on adduct formation. Still another additional feature in the CV of $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ -py system is that a hump is observed on the positive potential side close to zero potential. Several such humps were observed by Randle *et al.*⁷ in the CV of $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ at dropping mercury electrode and were characterised as adsorption waves.

Bis(dithiocarbamate)copper(II) perchlorate, $[\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$: We studied only two compounds in this class viz., $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$. This study has been aimed at comparison between the CV behaviours of $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$ and the corresponding $[\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$: In the potential range studied, two one-electron reversible redox couples have

been observed. The two couples obviously are

The two redox steps are thus the same as observed in the CV behaviour of $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$. A perusal of the CV data for $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$, shows that within the experimental error the potential parameters for both the complexes are same for both the redox couples. Both the anodic and cathodic peak currents are however considerably smaller for $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2\text{ClO}_4$ for both the redox couples. For $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ couple, the current values have gone down to less than half compared to those of $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$, while for $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ couple, the currents are reduced to less than one-third. A closer look at the cyclic voltammograms for the two complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$, also reveals that while both the redox couples for $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ yield well-defined clean redox cycles, the redox cycles for $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ suffer from adsorption effects. $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ couple shows post-reduction and pre-oxidation adsorption hump and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ couple shows pre-reduction and post-oxidation adsorption humps.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$: The cyclic voltammograms for this complex show complications due to adsorption. The voltammograms are distorted to such an extent that extraction of CV parameters has become difficult. Only the reduction step of the redox $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ couple, $[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2]^+ + e^- = \text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2$, is clearly discernible for which E_{pc} is 0.038 V, quite close to the E_{pc} of the same step in the CV of $\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2$. Although the oxidation step of this couple is accompanied with a strong post-adsorption wave, the E_{pa} for this step can still be estimated as 0.046 V, again close to that step in the CV of $\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2$. The second redox couple, $\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2 + e^- = [\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2]^-$, has been adsorption-distorted beyond recognition. The only report available so far on the CV behaviour of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2]^+$ species is that of Hendrickson *et al.*⁸ on $[\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2]\text{BF}_4$ complexes including $[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{BF}_4$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{BF}_4$. They however made no mention of the adsorption and the complications arising there from. The problem of adsorption has been elaborately discussed by Randle *et al.*⁷ in their CV work on $\text{Cu}(\text{dtc})_2$ at hanging mercury drop electrode.

Experimental

Preparation of complexes :

$[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]$: An aqueous solution of sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate dihydrate (0.02 mol) was added to the aqueous solution of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol) with stirring. The resulting red-brown precipitate was washed several times with water and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

$[\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2]\text{ClO}_4$: A chloroform solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{et}_2\text{dtc})_2$ (0.02 mol) was added with stirring to

an ethanolic solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol). The dark green crystalline precipitate formed immediately, was washed with alcohol and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 . Proper precaution was taken as the compound detonates violently on heating or crushing.

$[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dte})_2]$: An ethanolic solution of sodium dicyclohexyl dithiocarbamate dihydrate (0.02 mol) was added to an aqueous solution of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol). The resulting brown precipitate was washed with ethanol (1 : 1) and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

$[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dte})_2]\text{ClO}_4$: It was prepared by the thiuram disulphide method reported earlier⁴. Tetracyclohexyl thiuramdisulphide was first obtained in the following way. An aqueous solution of sodium dicyclohexyl dithiocarbamate was treated with potassium ferricyanide (slight excess) at 0–25°. A white precipitate was obtained, which was washed several times with water, dried in air and recrystallised from a benzene solution by addition of cyclohexane. $[\text{Cu}(\text{chx}_2\text{dte})_2]\text{ClO}_4$ was prepared by adding acetone solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol) to the benzene solution of tetracyclohexyl thiuram disulphide. The resulting green crystalline precipitate was washed with benzene and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

Cyclic voltammetric studies :

Cyclic voltammetric experiments were carried out with a CV-1B cyclic voltammetry system having an electrochemical cell with three-electrode system. The working electrode was a platinum microelectrode (MFZ 013), platinum wire as auxiliary electrode and SCE as reference electrode. The cyclic voltammograms were recorded on X-Y recorder supplied with this instrument. All the cyclic voltammetry experiments were done in an inert atmosphere by bubbling extra pure nitrogen for nearly 15 min in the cell solution before recording the cyclic voltammograms. An inert atmosphere of nitrogen

was also maintained over the cell solution during recording of the voltammograms by passing nitrogen through the blanket tube. Tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) (Fluka) was used as the supporting electrolyte. High purity acetone and pyridine (E. Merk/B.D.H.) were used as such. All the cyclic voltammetric experiments were performed at a constant temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ$).

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